

A Study on Evaluation of Green Products and Green Marketing

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Abstract

Increasing awareness on the various environmental problems has led a shift in the way consumers go about their life. There has been a change in consumer attitude towards a green lifestyle. People are actively trying to reduce their impact on the environment. However, this is not widespread and is still evolving. Organisations and business, however, have seen this change in consumer attitudes and are trying to gain an edge in the competitive market by exploiting the potential in the green market industry. In this research paper, the main emphasis has been made on the concept, need, and importance of green marketing. Data has been collected from multiple sources of evidence, in addition to books, journals, websites, and newspaper. The paper describes the study on the evolution of green products and green marketing.

Introduction

Green Marketing is a Golden goose. According to the American Marketing Association, green marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. Thus green marketing incorporates a board range of activities, including product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising.

Green Marketing involves developed and promoting products and services that satisfy customers want and need for Quality, Performance, Affordable Pricing and Convenience without having a detrimental input on the environment.

Evolution of Green Marketing

The green marketing has evolved over a period. According to Peattie (2001), the evaluation of green marketing has three phases. The first phase was termed as "Ecological" green marketing, and during this period all marketing activities were concerned to help environment problems and provide remedies for environmental

problems. The second phase was “Environmental” Green marketing and the focus shifted on clean technology that involved designing of innovative new products while taking care of pollution and waste issues. The third phase was “Sustainable” green marketing. It came into prominence in the late 1990’s and early 2000.

According to Joel Malkovar (cited by shafaat & Sultan, 2012), challenges faced by green marketer also include the lack of standards and common consensus among the public about what constitutes “green.” Despite these challenges, green marketing continues to gain popularity, particularly in light of growing global concern about climate change. Companies are coming forward to showcase their commitments to reduce adverse climate impacts of their products and services. Green marketing can play an important role in sustainable development so firms must adopt innovative methods to sustain itself in the competitive environment.

Green Products and its Characteristics

The products those are manufactured with green technology and that caused no environmental hazards are called green products. Promotions of green technology and green products are necessary for conservations of natural resources and sustainable development; we can define green products by following measures:

- Products those are originally grown
- Products those are recyclable, reusable and biodegradable
- Products with natural ingredients
- Products containing recycled
- Products contents under approval chemical
- Products that do not harm or pollute the environment
- Products that will not be tested on animals
- Products that have eco-friendly packaging, i.e., reusable, refillable containers, etc.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the concepts of green marketing.
2. A Study on Evaluation of green products.

Research Methodology

The research is exploratory, it focuses on Literature review, News Papers, Journals, websites and other reliable sources.

Green Products

Green Products are those that have less of an impact on the environment or are less determined by human health than traditional equivalent. Green products might, typically, be formed or part-formed from recycled components, be manufactured in a more energy-conservative way, be supplied to the market with less packaging, or be manufactured from local materials to reduce the need for transportation and reduce carbon footprints (or all four).

Green Products and Marketing Practices

There is no consensus on what exactly is green. There is no accepted definition of the green product. However based on different definitions of green marketing, some common characteristics of products generally accepted as green, including the products are:

- Energy efficient (both in use and in production)
- Water efficient (both in use and in production)

- Safe and healthy products
- Recyclable
- Durable
- Biodegradable
- Renewable
- Reused products
- Locally produced

Green Products in India

- Wipro Info tech (Green It) was India's first company to launch environmentally friendly computer peripherals.
- Samsung was the first to launch ecofriendly mobile handsets (made of renewable materials)
- Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd (ONGC), India's largest oil company, has introduced energy- efficient Mokshada Green Crematorium, which saves 60% to 70% of wood and a fourth of the burning time per cremation.
- Honda India introduced its Civic Hybrid car.
- ITC has introduced Paper Kraft, a premium range of ecofriendly business paper.
- Indusland Bank installed the country's first solar-powered ATM and thus brought about an eco-savvy change in the Indian banking sector.

Ways to go Green

- Unplug when not in use
- Use less water, every drop water
- Choose products with less packaging
- Buy organic and local food
- Spread the world about green, live green, stay green.

Examples of Best Eco-Friendly Products in India

Eco-Friendly Clothing

Most clothing is made from cotton, but there is a surprising percentage that's made out of flexible plastic sheeting and plasticized fabric. The ecofriendly products in this section will either help you avoid clothing made out of plastic or help you to reduce clothing waste in our landfills.

Clothes Made from Recycled Fabric

Recover Brands produces clothing that's made entirely out of recycled material. They also use the most environmentally sustainable manufacturing methods possible by eliminating the use of dyes and minimizing chemicals, water and energy use.

Drink Bottles and Accessories

American alone throws away 35 billion plastic bottles each year. Not only does this plastic end up in landfills, in our oceans, and in other parts of the environment where it can cause damage, it also contains BPA. BPA is a potentially harmful chemical found in many plastic products that can leak into your water and other beverages. The following products can help you eliminate your plastic bottle pollution and keep you and your family safe from harmful chemicals.

Stainless Steel Drinking Bottles

Our H2 Onya stainless steel drink bottle is 100% BPA free. This makes it a safe, Sustainable way to consume your favorite beverages on the go. It also comes in three sizes to cater to different levels.

Challenges of Green Marketing

- Green products require renewable and recyclable material, which is costly.
- Problems of deceptive advertising and false claims.
- Require a technology, which requires huge investments in research and development
- Majority of the people are not aware of green products and their uses.
- Majority of the consumers are not willing to pay a premium for green marketing.

Suggestions

Green marketing is still in its infancy and a lot of research is to be done on green marketing to fully explore its potential. There are some suggestions that organisations should implement for catering challenges of green marketing and successful exploitation of green marketing. The consumer needs to be made more aware of the merits of Green products. The consumer needs to be educated and made aware of the environmental threats. For the effective and efficient implementation of this concept of green marketing the factor that plays a major role is the Government. Unless the government creates specific and stringent laws and utilizes its authority to implement them, the concept cannot be conceptualized.

Conclusion

Green marketing is a tool for protecting the environment for future generation. It is not going to be an easy concept. The firm has to plan and then carry out research to find out how feasible it is going to be. Green marketing has to evolve since it is still in its infancy stage. Adoption of Green marketing may not be easy in the short run, but in the long run, it will have a positive impact on the firm. Green marketing is still in the stage of childhood in the Indian companies. Lots of opportunities are available. Now, this is the right time to select Green marketing globally. It will come with the drastic change in the world of business if all nations make strict rules because green marketing is essential to save the world from pollution.

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